

АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 7 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 7

JOURNAL OF AGRO PROCESSING

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 7

АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ | JOURNAL OF AGRO PROCESSING

№7 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9904-2022-7>

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THEORY QUESTIONS OF THE REPLACEMENT OF THE MAIN EQUIPMENT OF PUMPING STATIONS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7340584>

ABSTRACT

In order to timely solve any problems that arise when using pumping units is impossible without conducting supervisory and analytical work. A modern and perfect way of detecting pumps that are not working properly in the units is diagnosing. The article gives the results of the work done on the development of a diagnostic system for pumping units at pumping stations. The use of the proposed diagnostic system leads to a reduction in costs when using pumping units and the costs of their maintenance.

Keywords: automatic diagnostics, degradation, monitoring, reliability, forecast, staged failure, pumping unit, control technique, technical condition, trend, equipment, mathematical model, testing, device, probability of failure-free operation.

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НАСОС СТАНЦИЯЛАРИНИНГ АСОСИЙ ЖИҲОЗЛАРИНИ АЛМАШТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Назорат ва таҳлил ишларини олиб бормасдан туриб насос агрегатларидан фойдаланиш даврида келиб чиқадиган хар хил муоммоларни ечиб бўлмайди. Насос агрегатларида содир бўладиган асосий бузилишларни аниқлашнинг замонавий ва мукамал усули бу, уларни диагностика қилиш ҳисобланади. Мақола насос станцияларидаги насос агрегатларини диагностика қилиш тизимини ишлаб чиқишга қаратилган. Таклиф этилаётган диагностика қилиш тизимидан фойдаланиш натижасида насос агрегатларидан фойдаланиш кўрсаткичларининг ошишга ва таъмирлашга сарф қилинган ҳаражатларни камайтиришга эришилади.

Калит сўзлар: автоматик диагностика, дегредатция, техник ҳолат, мониторинг, ишонччилик, олдиндан башорат қилиш, ишламай қолиш, насос агрегати, назорат қилиш

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ВОПРОСЫ ТЕОРИИ ЗАМЕНЫ ОСНОВНЫХ ОБОРУДОВАНИЙ НАСОСНЫХ СТАНЦИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Своевременное решение проблем, возникающих при использовании насосных агрегатов невозможно без проведения надзорных и аналитических работ. Современным и совершенным способом обнаружения недосдатков в работе агрегатов насосов является диагностирование. В статье приведены результаты работ по разработке диагностической системы насосных агрегатов на насосных станциях. Внедрение по предлагаемой диагностической системы приведёт к снижению затрат при эксплуатации насосных агрегатов и расходов на их техническое обслуживание.

Ключевые слова: автоматическая диагностика, деградация, мониторинг, надежность, прогноз, стадийный отказ, насосный агрегат, методика контроля, техническое состояние, тренд, оборудование, математическая модель, испытание, устройство, вероятность безотказной работы.

Introduction. The technical condition of the pumping units (PU) is determined by comparing the actual parameters (head H , feed, consumed by active power) with the calculated, as well as the physical state of the greatest, which are determined in the course of preventive measures and diagnostics of PU.

Criteria for assessing the technical condition of centrifugal pumps are the maximum deviations in pressure and efficiency from the passport value. When the pressure drops above 2% and the efficiency is more than 3%, the technical condition of the pump is considered unsatisfactory and its further operation is prohibited.

When determining reliability tests, reliability indicators should be specified, terms and volumes of repairs, The need for spare parts is determined, for the purpose of making these data in the technical documentation. Reliability testing is the longest, since they determine the operating time for failure, usually equal to 4000-8000 h., and operating time before major repairs (20-30 thou. h.). For this purpose, choose controlled stations, where the pumps are regularly monitored:

- General, which includes determining the efficiency and basic parameters and characteristics of equipment to identify its qualities and properties, and getting more efficient use.
- Operational, conducted on the basis of the results of general tests during operation, to expand the characteristics obtained, for other operating conditions of the aggregates and revealing the wear and tear of the mechanisms and their condition after the revision.
- Research trials of an individual nature, aimed at further improving the efficiency and safety of operation of the PU.

To solve the task and increase the accuracy of diagnosis, we created a model "Device for the diagnosis of pump units" [1].

Methods and materials.

The device includes a differentiating unit and a comparison unit, which are equipped with an electronic counting device installed on the suction and pressure lines of the pump. This is an absolutely accurate means of determining the flow parameters of the pump, since the use of induction, ultrasonic modern flow meters, significant limitations are imposed on abrasive impurities, temperature and other characteristics of the liquid being measured under real operating conditions of

pumps. The use of an electronic counting device makes it possible to reduce the measurement error and increase the efficiency of the change in the mode.

The authors developed a software module and a program for dynamic monitoring of the efficiency of large PU [2]. The operational tolerances of the parameters (operational tolerances) do not take into account the measurement errors. The rejection tolerances of the parameters are the sum of the operational allowable deviation and the maximum permissible standard deviation of the measuring instruments. Without specifying operational tolerances, it is not possible to define and determine longevity indicators, since the life of the pump becomes an indefinite concept.

Results. It is assumed that the equipment is always in one of two possible states - healthy or damaged. The probability $P(t)$ that the equipment is in good working order during time t is called the equipment reliability function.

The reliability function $P(t)$ has the following properties:

$P(0)=1, P(\infty)=0, P(t)$ is twice differentiable, and $P'(t)<0$. The exponential function $P(t) = e^{-\lambda t}$ satisfies these properties. For any reliability function, the damage size is determined by the expression

$$f(t) = -\frac{P'(t)}{P(t)}; \tag{1}$$

and the size of the damage is a constant value.

For an exponential function, this value is equal to λ . Equipment that has more than one stochastic damaging part will be in good condition when all parts are in good condition. Then the reliability function of the machine $P(t)$ will depend on the reliability function of its elements.

$$P(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i(t); \tag{2}$$

Time can be either integer or continuous. Any equipment or replacement part is expected to function as good as new. A number of cases of equipment replacement are discussed below [3, 4].

The efficiency of replacing a single piece of equipment with a probabilistic damage process.

First consider the case of equipment replacement for a single piece of equipment with an arbitrary distribution of damage time. Since the replacement time also serves as the start of the recovery process, the optimal strategy will be strictly periodic, and this is sufficient to maximize the service life for a single cycle. If t is the time interval from the end of one replacement or repair to the beginning of another, then the average cycle health

$$F(t) = \frac{\int_0^T P(t)dt}{T + \Delta tp}; \tag{3}$$

where: Δtp is the replacement time.

Obviously, Δt is a positive value [5].

To maximize the average machine cycle uptime, we need to differentiate the uptime function $F(t)$ two times:

$$F'(t) = \frac{P(t)}{t + \Delta t} - \frac{F(t)}{t + \Delta t}; \tag{4}$$

$$F'(t) = \frac{P(t)}{t + \Delta t} - 2 \frac{F(t)}{t + \Delta t}; \tag{5}$$

Equating to zero (4), we get

$$P(t) = F(t); \tag{6}$$

or

$$(t + \Delta t) P(t) - \int_0^T P(t)dt; \tag{7}$$

The left side of expression (7) will be positive at $t=0$, because $\Delta t > 0$, and negative for large t , because $P(t)$ uniformly tends to zero, and is a $tP(t) - \int_0^t p(t)dt$ non-increasing function in t and equals zero at $t=0$.

For any other value of t_e we have

$$F'(t_e) = \frac{P'(t)}{t + \Delta t} < 0; \tag{8}$$

so that any similar solution leads to a maximum and gives a unique solution.

To illustrate, let's define the optimal replacement time for the exponential distribution function of the damage time. In this case, $P(t)=e^{-\lambda t}$ but to the maximum points $P(t)=F(t)$, hence.

$$e^{-\lambda t} = \frac{\int_0^t e^{-\lambda t} dt}{t + \Delta t} = \frac{[1 - e^{-\lambda t}]}{\lambda(t + \Delta t)}; \tag{9}$$

or

$$e^{-\lambda t} = 1 + (t_e + \Delta t_e)\lambda; \tag{10}$$

From this expression, the selection method determines the value of t_e . In general, the equation has the form

$$P(t) = \frac{\int_0^t P(t)dt}{t + \Delta t};$$

or

$$t = \frac{\int_0^t P(t)dt}{P(t)} - \Delta t; \tag{11}$$

Differentiating t_e with respect to Δt , we get

$$\frac{\partial t_e}{\partial \Delta t} = \frac{-P(t_e)}{(t_e + \Delta t)P(t_e)} = \frac{1}{t_e + (\Delta t f'(t_e))} > 0; \tag{12}$$

where: $f(t_e)$ is the amount of instantaneous damage at time t . Thus, the optimal replacement period increases with increasing equipment downtime Δt due to replacement. With an exponential function, the damage distribution includes only one parameter λ , i.e. $f(t_e)=\lambda$, consequently

$$\frac{\partial t_e}{\partial \Delta t} = \frac{1}{(t_e + \Delta t)\lambda}; \tag{13}$$

Then instead of (9) we can write

$$\frac{t_e}{\lambda} = \frac{\Delta t - t [e^{-\lambda t} - 1]}{\lambda [e^{-(\lambda t - 1)}]} < 0; \tag{14}$$

Since $F(t) = P(t)$, we get

$$t + t_p = e^{-\lambda t} \int_0^t e^{-\lambda t} dt < e^{-\lambda t} \cdot t; \tag{15}$$

so $t_p - t \left[e^{\lambda t} - 1 \right] < 0$; (15). Therefore, the optimal replacement time in the case of an exponential damage function increases with increasing damage time [6,7].

Discussions. Until now, only the replacement of equipment and damage, considered as deterministic processes, have been studied in detail.

For such equipment, certain characteristics were assumed before the entry into operation of the machine. In this case, the minimum cost of the machine during its service life, including the cost of subsequent replacements, is taken as a criterion for replacing equipment. However, in reality, damage to a machine cannot be accurately predicted when viewed as a deterministic process. This process, most likely, is stochastic (probabilistic), since it is caused by numerous factors that cannot be foreseen in advance.

There are numerous proposals for replacing the machine based on stochastic damage processes.

The cost density function $\phi(t)$, as one of the best proposals, is taken as the damage scale. This function takes into account all types of costs, replacement costs and salvage values of the old machine.

At each age t , $\phi(t)$, is a random variable with a distribution function $P\left(\frac{c}{t}\right)$, so $P\left(\frac{c}{t}\right) =$ probability $\{\phi(t) \leq c\}$. In other words, if we consider a large number of machines of the same type as the machine under study, then at age t a function with a cost density less than or equal to (c) will be very close to the function $P\left(\frac{c}{t}\right)$. Such a simple scheme is quite sufficient for practical calculations and there is no need to complicate the cost density distribution function too much.

The advantage of the process considered here is not only known $P\left(\frac{c}{t}\right)$, but also that it includes some probabilities, as will be seen from further considerations.

Let's denote the replacement cost without the return value of the old car as $3(c, t)$. In these expressions, c denotes $\phi(t)$. Then the total cost of the used machine at age t and its further replacement can be represented as

$$\int_0^t \phi(t_1) dt_1 + 3(\phi(t), t); \tag{16}$$

For the replacement process, we assume the expected cost of a machine of the same type.

As a criterion, a replacement is taken at which the density, the cost, reaches a given value C , i.e., the machine will be replaced after its wear reaches a certain amount provided in advance.

This formulation of the question is tantamount to obtaining a minimum expected value. Obviously, this can only be applied when the weight of the parts of the machine is available to measure the damage [8].

Denote $E\left(C \frac{T}{c}\right)$ by the expected total cost over time T to replace the cost density with and

$$\left[\frac{C}{c}\right] = \lim_{t \rightarrow 1} \frac{E\left(C \frac{T}{c}\right)}{T}; \tag{17}$$

as the average rate of value we denote in the same way,

$$A(t) = \int_0^t \phi(t_1) dt; \tag{18}$$

where $A(t)$ represents the total annual operating and cost over time t .

Then it can be proved that [*] expression (17) will take the form

$$\left[\frac{C}{c} \right] = \frac{E \left[\frac{A}{c} \right] + E \left[\phi \left(C \frac{t}{c} \right) \right]}{E \left[\frac{t}{c} \right]}; \tag{19}$$

where $E \left[\frac{t}{c} \right]; E \left[\frac{A}{c} \right]; E \left[\phi C \frac{t}{c} \right]$ - expectations $t, A(t) \phi(c, t)$ when the cost density reaches c .

The optimal replacement cost density C_t will be the value C for which $\left[\frac{C}{c} \right]$ reaches its minimum $[c]$.

Let's show how to determine the value $[c]$ on a numerical example. To establish the efficiency of the replacement, we use the inequalities $[t \leq c \leq kt]$ and $P \left[\frac{C}{t} \right] = 0$.

Excluding the value of t from the intervals, we get $\frac{C}{k} \leq t \leq c$. Let us consider the probability when the cost density reaches c in the time interval t and $t+dt$.

Since $\phi(t)$ increases with the age of the machine, a small change over time gives

$$\left[P \left(\frac{C}{t} + dt \right) - P \left(\frac{C}{t} \right) \right] = - \frac{dP \left(\frac{C}{t} \right)}{dt} dt; \tag{20}$$

So the values $E \left(\frac{t}{c} \right)$ will look like

$$E \left[\frac{t}{c} \right] = - \int_{\frac{c}{k}}^c t \cdot \frac{dP \left(\frac{C}{t} \right)}{dt} dt = \int_{\frac{c}{k}}^c \frac{C}{(k-1)} dt = \frac{C \ln(k)}{k-1};$$

And

$$E \left(\frac{A}{c} \right) = \frac{C^2 \ln(k)}{2(k-1)}$$

From the equation (17)

$$\left(\frac{A}{c} \right) = \frac{C}{2} + \frac{\phi(k-1)}{c \ln(k)}$$

Consequently $C_t = \left[\frac{2\phi(k-1)}{\ln(k)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$

$$[C] = [C(C_t)] = \left[\frac{2\phi(k-1)}{\ln(k)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

K - in these formulas shows the scale of change the scale of change in the cost density. This value is always greater than one [9].

These provisions formed the basis for the replacement of the main equipment of pumping stations in the Fergana Valley in the event of a probabilistic damage process.

Conclusion. Failure of a centrifugal pump unit due to fatigue failure of a rolling bearing does not occur suddenly and not instantly. First, some signs of the approach of this process appear, the nature of the vibration activity of the unit changes. Against the background of a stable vibration level, some outliers of vibration trends appear. The study of the sequence and intensity of these emissions is important information not only about the approach of the moment of destruction of the rolling bearing parts, but also about the operating time that the operating personnel still have to take measures to eliminate an emergency and complete catastrophic destruction.

The conducted studies of the process of changing the vibration of centrifugal pumping units showed, what is in operation, identifying patterns of multi-stage failure processes of rolling bearing parts by vibration trend emissions, using patterns of vibration trend emissions, starting from the first stage of the appearance of degradation, and subsequent monitoring of the development of defects for a timely assessment of the technical condition of the unit.

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ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 7

JOURNAL OF AGRO PROCESSING

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 7

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